

Preparation and antibacterial activity of sulfonamido derivatives and amides of coumarin compounds

Sonal Shah, Devki Desai and R. H. Mehta*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Vadodara-390 002, India

Manuscript received 18 May 1998, revised 17 June 1999, accepted 22 June 1999

Coumarins are naturally occurring compounds and known to have biological activities¹. On the other hand haloacetamides² possess amoebicidal activity and substituted acetamide³ have local anaesthetic activity. Sulfanilamide and its derivatives are of considerable medicinal importance as the sulfadruugs. Some coumarin derivatives possessing carboxamide moiety are found to have diuretic, analgesic, myorelaxant⁴, antifungal⁵ and anthelmintic⁶ activities. Coumarin derivatives possessing sulfonamide moiety are found to have antimicrobial⁷, antifungal⁸ and antitubercular⁹ activities. Essential amino acids are also biologically important. The present communication reports the preparation of some hitherto unknown sulfonamides and carboxamides involving 8-methoxycoumarin derivatives and evaluate their antibacterial activity.

Antibacterial activity : All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* using cup-plate method¹⁰ in DMF solvent. The sulfonamides were tested against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhosa* and *S. albus* while the carboxamides were tested against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* at 100 and 500 ppm concentration. The results are compared with ampicillin. The compounds showing moderate activity are 1a, 1c against *E. coli*, 1d, 1i, 2a, 2d against *S. aureus*, 1d, 1i, 1j against *S. typhosa* and 1d, 2a, 2d against *S. albus* at 100 ppm concentration. Compounds 1a, 1c, 1i, 2a, 2c, 2d, 3a-f, 3h-k against *E. coli*, 1d, 1i, 1j, 2a, 2d, 3h-k against *S. aureus*, 1d, 1i, 1j, 2a, 2d against *S. typhosa* and 1d, 1i, 2a, 2d against *S. albus* at 500 ppm concentration. Compounds 3a-k did not show any activity at 100 ppm concentration.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were performed on a Coleman instrument. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrometer and ¹H nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) and dpx 200 (200 MHz) spectrometers. Specific rotations was determined on a Jasco Dip-D polarimeter taking DMF as solvent at 25° and at λ = D line

- 1a R = H, R' = *p*-CH₃
 1b R = H, R' = *p*-OCH₃
 1c R = H, R' = *p*-NHCOCH₃
 1d R = H, R' = *p*-Cl
 1e R = H, R' = *p*-Br
 1f R = Br, R' = *p*-CH₃
 1g R = Br, R' = *p*-OCH₃
 1h R = Br, R' = *p*-NHCOCH₃
 1i R = Br, R' = *p*-Cl
 1j R = Br, R' = *p*-Br

- 2a R = *p*-CH₃
 2b R = *p*-OCH₃
 2c R = *p*-NHCOCH₃
 2d R = *p*-Cl
 2e R = *p*-Br

- 3a R = CH₃
 3b R = CH(CH₃)₂
 3c R = CH₂CH₂SCH₃
 3d R = CH₂OH
 3e R = CH(OH)CH₃
 3f R = H
 3g R = β-alanine
 3h R = CH₃
 3i R = CH(CH₃)₂
 3j R = CH₂CH₂SCH₃
 3k R = CH₂C₆H₅

*Compounds 3a-e contain L-aminoacids and 3h-k contain DL-amino acids.

of Na lamp. The homogeneity of the compound was tested using silica gel by tlc.

8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy-[o-(p'-substituted-benzenesulfonamido)]anilide (1a-j) : A mixture of 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy(o-amino)anilide (0.01 mol) and p-substituted sulphonyl chloride (0.01 mol) was refluxed in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) on an oil-bath at 120° for 3 h. The solid obtained on cooling was filtered and crystallised from proper solvent, ν_{\max} 3200–3000 (SO₂ NH and NH), 1700 (δ -lactone), 1653 (CONH), 1590 (C=C aryl) and 1280, 1100 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); **1a**, m.p. 295° (alcohol + DMF, yield 65%), δ (CF₃COOH, 90 MHz) 2.13 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.9–7.5 (ArH, m) and 8.9 (1H, s, C-4-H of coumarin ring); **1b**, 310° (DMF + H₂O, 60%); **1c**, 280° d (alcohol + DMF, 70%); **1d**, 295° (DMF, 80%); **1e**, 290° (DMF, 85%); **1f**, 282° (DMF, 81%); **1g**, 261° (DMF, 75%); **1h**, 202° (alcohol + H₂O, 75%); **1i**, 290° d (DMF + H₂O, 82%); **1j**, 275° d (DMF + H₂O, 85%).

8-Methoxy-5-[o-(p'-substituted-benzenesulfonamido)]anilinomethylcoumarin (2a-e) : A mixture of 8-methoxy-5-(o-amino)anilinomethylcoumarin (0.01 mol) and p-substituted-benzene sulfonylchloride (0.01 mol) was heated in pyridine (5 ml) on an oil-bath at 120° for 3 h. The resulting solid was treated with dil. HCl, filtered and crystallised from appropriate solvent, ν_{\max} 3400 and 3250 (SO₂NH and NH), 1710 (δ -lactone), 1605 (C=C aryl) and 1290 and 1095 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); **2a**, 197° (alcohol + H₂O, yield 65%); **2b**, 240° (DMF, 60%); **2c**, 266° (alcohol + DMF, 63%); **2d**, 224° (alcohol + DMF, 75%); **2e**, 224° (alcohol + DMF, 75%), δ (CF₃COOH, 90 MHz) 3.78 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.98 (2H, s, CH₂NH), 6.3–8.0 (m for ArH overlapping with d of C3-H of coumarin) and 7.95 (1H, d, C4-H of coumarin).

N-(8-Methoxy-3-coumarinoyl)glycine (3a-k) : The acid chloride of 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxylic acid was prepared according to the reported method⁵. To the acid chloride (0.01 mol) taken in dry diethyl ether (60 ml), glycine (0.01 mol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 4–5 h. The solid separated was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol to yield **3f**. Similarly, L-alanine, L-valine, L-methionine, L-serine and L-threonine were condensed to give the corresponding carboxamides (**3a-e**), and DL-alanine, DL-valine, DL-methionine and DL-phenylalanine condensed to give the carboxamides (**3h-k**) : ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 1710 (δ -lactone), 1660 and 1570 (CONH), 1600 (C=C aryl) and 1270, 1100 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); **3a**, m.p. 250° (alcohol,

yield 72%), $[\alpha] = +58.70^\circ$; **3b**, 180° (acetic acid, 90%), $[\alpha] = +30.61^\circ$, δ (CF₃COOH, 200 MHz) 1.0 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂CH), 2.35 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 4.01 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.61 (1H, m, CH-COOH), 7.2–7.5 (3H, m, ArH), 8.8 (1H, s, C4-H of coumarin ring), 9.2 (1H, d, NH of amide); **3c**, 190° (alcohol, 76%), $[\alpha] = +27.62^\circ$; **3d**, 250° (alcohol, 70%), $[\alpha] = +28.95^\circ$; **3e**, 260° (alcohol, 81%), $[\alpha] = +38.83^\circ$; **3f**, 242° (alcohol, 71%); **3g**, 215° (DMF + H₂O, 73%); **3h**, 230° (alcohol + H₂O, 80%); **3i**, 227° (alcohol + H₂O, 86%), δ (CF₃COOH, 90 MHz), 1.0 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂CH), 2.35 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.6 (1H, m, CH-COOH), 7.1–7.5 (3H, m, ArH of coumarin), 8.85 (1H, s, C4-H of coumarin); **3j**, 220° (alcohol + H₂O, 79%); **3k**, 175° (alcohol + H₂O, 83%).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. A. C. Shah, Head, Chemistry Department, M. S. University of Baroda, for his interest in the work, and to Prof. Murthy, Head, Pharmacy Department, M. S. University of Baroda for antibacterial activity. They are also thankful to Vice-President, MultiChem., Nandesari and to Director, SPARC, for the analytical data. Thanks are due to Dr. Madhava Rao for elemental analysis and nmr spectra.

References

1. A. Del Campo and P. L. Fazzi, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, **53**, 14213; S. S. Kumari, K. S. H. M. Rao and N. V. S. Rao, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1973, **77**, 149; M. Agrawal, S. B. Bansal and O. P. Singhal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 200.
2. P. Truitt, F. M. Wood and R. L. Hall, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1460; A. B. Sen and S. B. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 563.
3. N. M. Lofgren and B. J. Lund Vist, *Chem. Abstr.* 1948, **42**, 6378; P. N. Bhargava and M. R. Chadrasla, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, **58**, 896.
4. L. Bonsignore, G. Loy, D. Seci and A. Calignano, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **28**, 517
5. S. Shah and R. H. Mehta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 708.
6. M. F. Clotheir and L. Byunghyun, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, **117**, 787.
7. A. M. Shalaby, A. H. Mandour and H. A. Farrag, *Bull. Nat. Res. Cent.*, 1994, **19**, 97 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **122**, 81071), M. A. A. Moustafa, *Sci. Pharm.*, 1991, **59**, 213.
8. C. Shekhar, D. Lakkannuar, M. V. Kulkarni and V. P. Patil, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 399.
9. A. S. Gupta and M. S. Phull, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1996, **35**, 276.
10. F. Cavanagh, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963.